

Synthesis of Phthal-As-Eins*

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Manuscript received 23 September 1972; accepted 11 May 1973

New series of dyes, Phthal-As-Eins (PAE)-methyl phenol PAE, methyl resorcinol PAE, methyl catechol PAE, methyl quinol PAE, methyl phloroglucinol PAE, methyl pyrogallol PAE and methyl orcinol PAE have been obtained by condensing 2-acetyl benzoic acid with appropriate phenols. The structure of methyl resorcinol PAE, which was found to exist in two isomeric forms, based on chemical reactions and spectral data has been discussed. The λ_{max} values of most of the dyes were found higher than their analogous phthaleins.

THE two isomeric forms (I) and (II) of 2-acetyl benzoic acid (I) have been established by a number of workers¹⁻³. The lactol (II) on condensation with phenols gives a new series of compounds, phthal-as-eins (III). The condensation process proceeds through the equilibrium process of lactol (II) of acid (I) and with excess of phenol whole of the acid reacts as lactol.

Seven phthal-as-eins (PAE)-methyl phenol PAE (IV), methyl resorcinol PAE (V), methyl catechol PAE (VI), methyl quinol PAE (VII), methyl phloroglucinol PAE (VIII), methyl pyrogallol PAE (IX) methyl orcinol PAE (X) have been prepared by condensing acid (I) with respective phenols.

dye (V) confirmed by mixed m.p., superimposable IR and λ_{max} values. However, the acid (XIII) when acetylated in CO₂ atmosphere gave diacetyl compound (XIV; 1710 cm⁻¹). The diacetyl (XI; 1760, 1200 and 1125 cm⁻¹, γ -lactone and phenolic acetate) and dibromo (XII; 1760 cm⁻¹) derivatives of (V) are also indicative of γ -lactone and resorcinol molecule.

The pale yellow compound (V; 1770 cm⁻¹, lactoid) when boiled with excess of 0.01N HCl gave an isomeric orange-red compound (XV; 3600-3020 and 1690 cm⁻¹; -COOH and *p*-quinonoid) (cf. Fluorescein⁵).

The condensed products were purified using column chromatography supplemented with TLC. Their IR spectra show strong bands between 1770-1760 cm⁻¹ due to γ -lactone.

The methyl resorcinol PAE (V, 1770 cm⁻¹) was reduced by Zn-dust and acetic acid into an acid, methyl resorcinol phthal-as-ein⁴ (XIII; 3300-2900 and 1710 cm⁻¹ due to -COOH). The acid (XIII) when left overnight was found changed into original

The absorption maxima (λ_{max}) of PAE(III) given in Table I have been found shifted towards longer wave regions (cf. phthaleins).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The λ_{max} (UV and visible) have been recorded using model DU Beckmann Spectrophotometer in absolute ethanol and IR determined using a Perkin Elmer Infracord.

The phenols have been taken in a little excess of molecular proportion than the acid (I). Conc. H₂SO₄ (4-6 drops) has been used as condensing agent throughout and each dye, when tested, is found free from sulphur.

* Owing to unsymmetric central carbon atom (C⁴) present in (III) they may be named as phthal-as-eins; as representing unsymmetry and-ein the class of compound (phthal-ein).

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Methyl Resorcinol PAE (V): A mixture of acid (I) (5 g), resorcinol (4 g) and Conc. H₂SO₄ (4-6 drops) was heated at 140° for 3 hr. The condensed mass was extracted with 3% NaOH and precipitated with dil. HCl. The precipitate was chromatographed over silica gel with benzene: chloroform mixture (90:10). The residue of third fraction (200 ml) on crystallisation from 80% ethanol gave pale yellow crystalline dye (5.5 g; 65%), m.p. 310°. It gave a yellow colouration and light green fluorescence in ethanol which was intensified on the addition of alkali.

The preparation of rest of the dyes, given in Table 1, was done in identical manner as described in (V) above taking acid and appropriate phenols (Yield, 60-65%).

Chromatography of dye (IV): On test paper—Whatman No. 1, *n*-butanol-ammonia was allowed to run for 13 hr. (Descending) to give two corresponding spots (with 1% NaOH) of dye (IV) and reference dye phenol-phthalein; (R_f: (IV), 0.71; phenol-phthalein, 0.93 (lit.⁶, R_f, 0.92).

Acetylation of dye (V): The dye (V) (1 g), acetic anhydride (15 ml) and fused sodium acetate (2 g) were refluxed at 130°-140° for 3 hr. to give colourless diacetyl compound (XI). It was crystallised from 80% ethanol into a crystalline substance (0.9 g), m.p. 130° (λ_{max} 325 nm). (Found: C, 67.39; H, 4.58; CH₃CO, 25.88. C₁₉H₁₆O₆ required C, 67.06; H, 4.69; CH₃CO, 25.29%).

Bromination of dye (V): The dye (V) (1 g) was refluxed with 10% solution of bromine in glacial

 TABLE 1. PREPARATION, PROPERTIES AND λ_{max} VALUES OF METHYL PHTHAL-AS-EINS

Dyes	Condensation		M.P. (°C)	Appearance	λ _{max} (mμ)		Found (%)		Calcd. (%)	
	Temp. (°C)	Time (hr)			Neutral	at (pH)	C	H	C	H
(IV)*	120	8	90	White	—	480 560(11.5)	74.86	4.72	75.00	5.00
(V)	140	3	310	Pale yellow	450	495 (9.1)	70.89	4.68	70.31	4.69
(VI)	140	3	195	Light brown	—	440(10.3)	69.18	4.21	70.31	4.69
(VII)	140	3	225	Yellow red	—	420 (9.6)	69.83	4.18	70.31	4.69
(VIII)	150	2	255	Shining red	—	475 (8.9)	65.83	4.04	66.17	4.41
(IX)	140	3	195	Deep yellow	—	430 (9.8)	66.56	4.30	66.17	4.41
(X)	140	1	250	Scarlet red	—	495 (8.8)	70.82	4.69	71.11	5.18

* Excess phenol after condensation was removed by steam distillation.

(IV) R₁ = R₂ = R₄ = R₅ = H; R₃ = OH
 (V) R₂ = R₄ = R₅ = H; R₁ = R₃ = OH
 (VI) R₃ = R₄ = R₅ = H; R₁ = R₂ = OH
 (VII) R₂ = R₃ = R₅ = H; R₁ = R₄ = OH
 (VIII) R₂ = R₄ = H; R₁ = R₃ = R₅ = OH

(IX) R₄ = R₅ = H; R₁ = R₂ = R₃ = OH
 (X) R₂ = R₄ = H; R₅ = CH₃; R₁ = R₃ = OH
 (XI) R₂ = R₄ = R₅ = H; R₁ = R₃ = OCOCH₃
 (XII) R₅ = H; R₂ = R₄ = Br; R₁ = R₃ = OH

acetic acid (10 ml) at 130°–140° for 1 hr. to give (1 g) a light orange dibromo compound (XII) (from 80% ethanol), m.p. 185° (λ_{max} , at neutral and at pH 7.5, 520 nm), which dissolved in ethanol with light pink colour and light green fluorescence and get intensified on addition of NaOH. (Found : Br, 38.14; $C_{15}H_{10}O_4Br_2$ requires Br, 38.62%).

Zinc-dust reduction of dye (V) : The dye (V) (2 g) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid (100 ml) and Zn-dust (5 g) for 20 min to give (1.6 g) glistening colourless crystalline product (XIII) (from acetic acid in CO_2 atmosphere) m.p. 165°, which is acidic in nature and do not give fluorescence in alkaline solution. (Found : C, 69.33; H, 4.98, $C_{15}H_{14}O_4$ required C, 69.76; H, 5.43%).

The acid (XIII) when left overnight was found changed to pale yellow compound. This coloured compound and its acetyl derivative were found identical to parent dye (V) and its acetyl derivative (XI) confirmed by mixed m.p. λ_{max} values and super-imposable IR (Found : C, 70.62; H, 4.66. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ required C, 70.31; H, 4.69%).

Acetylation of acid (XIII) : The acid (XIII) (0.5 g) acetic anhydride (10 ml) and fused sodium acetate (2 g) were heated in CO_2 atmosphere at 130°–135° for 3 hr. to give diacetyl compound (XIV). It was crystallised as white glistening plates from acetic acid (0.48 g) m.p. 155°. (Found : C, 66.23; H, 4.75; CH_3CO , 25.62. $C_{29}H_{18}O_6$ required C, 66.6; H, 5.26; CH_3CO , 25.14%).

Red resorcinol PAE (XV) : The dye (V; yellow form) (0.5 g) was dissolved in 10% NaOH (20 ml) heated to boiling with steam and precipitated with a slight excess of boiling HCl to give orange red substance (XV), which was also obtained by boiling the yellow form with a large quantity of water containing a little HCl. It was washed well with boiling water dried over P_2O_5 under vacuum for 24 hr. (0.5 g), melted > 310°. The yellow form is re-obtained by the addition of acid to a cold alkaline solution of red form (XV). (Found : C, 70.75; H, 4.71. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ required C, 70.31; H, 4.6%).

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks to Dr. J. D Tewari for his useful suggestions. A grant and fellowship to (R.G.) from C.S.I.R., New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. S. GABRIEL, *Ber.*, 1881, **14**, 919.
2. Y. K. SYRKIN, *Russ. J. Phys. Chem.*, 1943, **17**, 347; *Chem Abs.*, 1944, **38**, 5701.
3. R. KUHN and H. SCHRETZMANN, *Ber.*, 1957, **90**, 557.
4. The nomenclature is according to 'The Chemistry of Carbon Compounds', Edited by E. H. Rodd, Vol. III-B, Elsevier, New York, 1110, 1956.
5. W. R. ORNDROFF and A. J. HEMMER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 1272.
6. L. HOUGH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2511; M. LEDERER, *Science*, 1950, **112**, 404.